

1 **Removal of diclofenac from different pharmaceutical matrices**
2 **using non-thermal plasma technology: ecotoxicity studies, cost-**
3 **benefit analysis, and current market scenario**

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5 Karina Lenard¹, Yash Chawla², Magda Caban³, Dominik Terefinko¹, Agata
6 Motyka-Pomagruk^{4,5}, Pawel Pohl¹, Piotr Cyganowski⁶, Piotr Jamroz¹, Anna
7 Dzimitrowicz^{1*}

8
9 *¹Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Department of Analytical Chemistry and*
10 *Chemical Metallurgy, 27 Wybrzeze St. Wyspianskiego, 50-370 Wroclaw, Poland;*

11
12 *²Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Department of Operation Research, 27*
13 *Wybrzeze St. Wyspianskiego, 50-370 Wroclaw, Poland;*

14
15 *³University of Gdansk, Faculty of Chemistry, Department of Environmental Analysis, 63 Wita*
16 *Stwosza, 80-308 Gdansk, Poland;*

17
18 *⁴University of Gdansk, Intercollegiate Faculty of Biotechnology University of Gdansk and*
19 *Medical University of Gdansk, Laboratory of Plant Protection and Biotechnology, 58*
20 *Abrahama, 80-307 Gdansk, Poland;*

21
22 *⁵University of Gdansk, Intercollegiate Faculty of Biotechnology University of Gdansk and*
23 *Medical University of Gdansk, Research and Development Laboratory, 20 Podwale*
24 *Przedmiejskie 20, 80-824 Gdansk, Poland;*

25 ⁶Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Chemistry, Department of
26 Process Engineering and Technology of Polymer and Carbon Materials, 27 Wybrzeze St.
27 Wyspianskiego, 50-370 Wroclaw, Poland;

28

29 *Corresponding Author: prof. Anna Dzimitrowicz: phone +48 71-320-24-53; e-mail address:

30 anna.dzimitrowicz@pwr.edu.pl

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33 **Highlights:**

34 - Non-thermal plasma was used for diclofenac removal from two pharmaceutical matrices

35 - Diclofenac removal efficiency was found to be different for analyzed matrices

36 - Purified solutions did not exhibit ecotoxicity towards *Lepidium sativum* seeds

37 - Cost-benefit analyses predicted putative implementation to the market

38

39 **Abbreviations:**

40 ACN - acetonitrile

41 AOP - advanced oxidation process

42 APPJ - atmospheric pressure plasma jet

43 CAGR - compound annual growth rate

44 CBA - cost-benefit analysis

45 CD - corona discharge

46 DCF - diclofenac

47 FLC-dc-APGD – flowing liquid cathode direct current atmospheric pressure glow discharge

48 HPLC-DAD - high-performance liquid chromatography with diode array detection

49 LOD - limit of detection

50 LOQ - limit of quantification

51 NPOC - non-purgeable organic carbon

52 NSAID - non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug

53 NTP - non-thermal plasma

54 OES - optical emission spectrometry

55 PCD - pulsed corona discharge

56 pm-rf-APGD - pulsed-modulated radio-frequency atmospheric pressure glow discharge

57 RNS - reactive nitrogen species

58 RONS - reactive oxygen and nitrogen species

59 ROS - reactive oxygen species

60 RSD - relative standard deviation

61 SD - standard deviation

62 TOC - total organic carbon

63 TN - total nitrogen

64 UV/Vis - ultraviolet/visible

65

66 **Abstract:**

67 Diclofenac (DCF) enters aquatic ecosystems and negatively affects wildlife. To tackle with
68 this environmental issue, it is required to develop novel methods for removal of DCF from
69 wastewaters. Here, continuous flow reaction discharge system with non-thermal plasma
70 (NTP), employing flowing liquid cathode (FLC) direct current atmospheric pressure glow
71 discharge (dc-APGD), was adopted for this purpose. The NTP-subjected DCF solutions have
72 been prepared basing on two pharmaceutical matrices to mimic the impact of diverse sources
73 of contamination in addition to contribution of the presence of differing excipients. Using
74 high-performance liquid chromatography with diode array detection (HPLC-DAD) 96-98%
75 removal efficiencies were determined for 50-200 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions prepared from gel in
76 comparison to 90-94% in terms of the 25-100 mg L⁻¹ DCF based on capsules matrix. Also,
77 the changing of selected parameters of the DCF solutions following NTP treatment were
78 shown. It was found that H₂O₂ and NO₂⁻ were involved in the DCF removal process.
79 Additionally, it was noted that DCF solutions subjected to NTP treatment exhibit no negative
80 impact on early growth of *Lepidium sativum* model plants seeds. Furthermore, we did a cost-
81 benefit analysis and suggested the current market scene by comparing our NTP-based
82 removal method to commonly applied methods.

83

84 **Graphical abstract:**

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86

87 **Keywords:** cold atmospheric pressure plasma; non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs;

88 reactive oxygen and nitrogen species; seeds; management;

89

90 **1. Introduction**

91 Diclofenac (DCF) is present on the market since 1970s. In 2022, with 4 295 892 patients
92 using this medicine, DCF was ranked as 51st most often prescribed medication in the United
93 States of America [1]. Throughout the world, on average 1443 ± 58 tonnes of DCF per year
94 in 2010-2013 [2] have been used [2]. Estimations point that the DCF market size will equal
95 \$6.1 billion by 2027, post raise due to annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.9% [3].

96 DCF is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), which shows a role of a
97 non-selective inhibitor of cyclooxygenases, being enzymes involved in transformation of
98 arachidonic acid to thromboxanes, prostacyclins, and prostaglandins [4]. For this reason, a
99 limited yield of prostaglandins decreases the associated sensitization of peripheral
100 nociceptors, leading to mechanical or painful stimuli, as was reported by Revel *et al.*, (2020)
101 [4]. What should also be emphasized, this mechanism of action resulted in the utilization of
102 DCF for therapy of various, commonly observed signs of sickness [5-6].

103 DCF is available in numerous formulations, *e.g.* capsules and tablets for oral
104 administration, suppositories, ophthalmic solutions, intravenous infusions, transdermal
105 patches or gel products, which are selected accordingly to the encountered disease symptoms.
106 Long-term usage of orally administered DCF preparations is discouraged due to risks linked
107 with general side effects, as was described in details by Pradal *et al.*, (2019) [7]. Thus, topical
108 applications of DCF-based formulations might be preferred if possible, as their clinical
109 efficacy is comparable, while systemic adverse effects in addition to multi-drug interactions
110 tend to be minimised [7]. Anyhow, the formulation of the administered medication with the
111 impact of the selected features seems not only to influence bioavailability of the active
112 substance for the patient, but also find reflection in the enhanced penetration of the drug
113 residuals to the aquatic ecosystems [7].

114 Therapeutic application of DCF ends up in introduction of the active molecule or the
115 corresponding transformation products, together with urine or faeces, following hygienic
116 procedures or improper drug disposal, into wastewaters [8]. Three quarters of the utilized
117 DCF were assessed to enter the specific ecosystems, including water and soil [8]. Regarding
118 the aquatic ecosystems, it is worth to notice that the determined DCF concentrations in the
119 Baltic Sea close to the Gdansk region (Poland) reached even 20 kg and originated from
120 sewage treatment plants [9]. Owing to low efficacy of wastewater treatment plants in
121 deactivation of biologically active pharmaceuticals, the residuals of DCF have been identified
122 in the different global aquatic ecosystems. As was reported by Acuna *et al.*, (2015) [2], the
123 median content of DCF determined in the aquatic ecosystems was reported as $21 \text{ ng L}^{-1} \pm 722$
124 ng L^{-1} , based on data related to 1264 samples collected in the different 38 countries [2].
125 Though, local concentrations of this drug may be much higher. For instance in Czech
126 Republic, among the surface water samples originating from 29 different locations of the
127 Elbe river basin, the maximum of determined DCF content was found to be in the range from
128 514 to 1080 ng L^{-1} , which is high [10].

129 To this point, environmental risks related to the environmental occurrence of DCF
130 involved mostly higher plants, birds, mammals, and aquatic organisms [11]. Additionally,
131 tendency to bioaccumulate in the non-targeted organisms within the food chain has been
132 underlined [12]. Up to the present time, most critical DCF-caused ecological damage was
133 reported in the selected Asian countries, in the populations of vultures, which were brought to
134 the edge of extinction owing to renal failure related to the consumption of the DCF-treated
135 livestock [13]. Disappointingly, DFC was revealed to be toxic to aquatic life even at the dose
136 of ng L^{-1} , previously assessed in the environmental samples [14]. Presently, the
137 consciousness of DCF-related risks is higher. Additionally, this drug has been put in the
138 European Union's (EU) first watch lists for emerging pollutants [15].

139 To remove DCF residues for wastewaters, various approaches have been developed
140 up to now, which are classified mainly to advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) *e.g.*
141 photodegradation [16-18], photo-Fenton degradation [19-20], photocatalysis with TiO₂ [21-
142 22], ozonation [23], sonolysis [24-27], among others. As a novel type of AOP, utilization of
143 non-thermal plasmas (NTPs) for DCF degradation has been recently studied [28]. As a result
144 of NTP exposure Reactive Oxygen and Nitrogen Species (RONS) are produced, which
145 participate in DCF degradation pathways [29]. Across various NTP sources, specific
146 consideration should be provided to the uses of circulating NTP-based systems, proposed so
147 far for DCF removal [30-32]. In these approaches, DCF is subjected to pulse-modulated
148 radio-frequency atmospheric pressure glow discharge (pm-rf-APGD) [30], the 3-pins
149 atmospheric pressure plasma jets (APPJs) [31], or the corona discharges (CDs) [32].
150 However, in the above-mentioned studies, DCF originated directly from pure sodium salts,
151 not from the original medication, which to the limited extent mimics the real life situation
152 [30-32].

153 Here, we present a novel approach for DCF removal from aqueous solutions prepared
154 from gel or capsules pharmaceutical matrices that rely on direct current atmospheric pressure
155 glow discharge (dc-APGD) formed in contact with a flowing liquid cathode (FLC). Versatile
156 advantage of FLC-dc-APGD is associated with the production of positive ions from the
157 plasma zone [33] besides generation of solvated electrons (e_{aq}^-) involved in the further
158 cascade reactions with the other RONS [29, 34]. Further benefits include the continuously
159 flowing DCF solutions, which assures high-throughput of the proposed approach. Having this
160 in mind, we hypothesized that by using FLC-dc-APGD we would achieve almost complete
161 DCF removal from aqueous solutions, prepared from different pharmaceutical matrices. For
162 this reason, we estimated the removal efficiency of DCF following FLC-dc-APGD treatment
163 and changes in the physicochemical properties of the NTP-treated DCF solutions. Then, we

164 determined putative environmental impact of the NTP-treated solutions by assessment of the
165 effects on the early growth of *Lepidium sativum* model plants. Finally, we performed detailed
166 cost-benefit analyses and estimated the current market scenario of the NTP-based DCF
167 removal method. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work, in which the removal
168 efficiency of DCF from different pharmaceutical matrices following NTP treatment was
169 determined. Furthermore, in this pioneering work reveals the possibilities of implementing
170 FLC-dc-APGD method into the industry or wastewaters treatment plants.

171

172 **2. Experimental**

173 **2.1. Reagents and Solutions**

174 Commercially available medical formulations either in a form of gel or capsules was used for
175 preparation of DCF-containing aqueous solutions. The active component of the gel was DCF
176 diethylammonium salt at the concentration of 2.32%, while the excipients included isopropyl
177 alcohol, oleic alcohol, diethylamine, propylene glycol, macrogol cetostearyl ether,
178 cocosylcaprylocaproate, carbomer, butylhydroxytoluene, liquid paraffin, eucalyptus fragrance
179 composition, and water, among others. For further analyses, three gel-based aqueous
180 solutions were prepared by weighing gel prior to suspending it in distilled water to reach 50,
181 100 or 200 mg L⁻¹ of DCF. Regarding capsules, the active component was diclofenac sodium
182 salt at the concentration 43.86 (m/m)%, whereas the excipients involved corn starch,
183 saccharose, talc, shellac, ammonium methacrylate copolymer, titanium dioxide, gelatine, and
184 sodium hydroxide, among others. The three capsules-based aqueous solutions were obtained
185 by weighing capsules before crushing and suspending their contents in distilled water to
186 finally achieve 25, 50, or 100 mg L⁻¹ of DCF.

187 To conduct high-performance liquid chromatography with a diode array detector
188 (HPLC-DAD), acetonitrile (ACN), ammonium formate and formic acid of HPLC grades

189 were purchased from VWR Chemicals (Poland). The HPLC-DAD calibration curve was
190 prepared using DCF standards, based on DCF sodium salt (CAS: 15307-79-6, MW: 318.3 g
191 mol⁻¹) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). In order to estimate the content of H₂O₂ in
192 the analyzed solutions, ammonium metavanadate (NH₄VO₃, CAS: 7803-55-6) and sulphuric
193 acid (H₂SO₄, CAS: 7664-93-9) were bought from Avantor Performance Materials (Poland).
194 Aiming to determine the content of NO₂⁻ in the studied solutions, sulphanilamide (CAS: 63-
195 74-1) and N-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (CAS: 1465-25-4) have been
196 acquired from Pol-Aura (Poland). Furthermore, hydrochloric acid (HCl, CAS: 7647-01-0)
197 was purchased from Idalia (Poland). In the interest of estimating the total reactive oxygen
198 species (ROS) content, starch (CAS: 9005-84-9) in addition to potassium iodide (KI, CAS:
199 7681-11-0) were obtained from Chempur (Poland). To sterilize plant seeds, ethanol
200 (C₂H₅OH, CAS: 64-17-5) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, CAS: 7722-84-1) from Avantor
201 Performance Materials (Poland) were used. De-ionized water of conductivity 0.05 μS cm⁻¹
202 has been utilized for all the analyses.

203

204 **2.2. FLC-dc-APGD-type reaction-discharge system dedicated for DCF removal** 205 **from different matrices**

206 Here, the NTP reaction-discharge system previously developed [30, 35, 36] has been
207 employed for removal of DCF from aqueous solutions prepared from diverse drug-containing
208 formulations (either in a form of gel or capsules; final concentrations of DCF from 25 to 200
209 mg L⁻¹). Notably, in the current work FLC-dc-APGD was applied as the NTP source (Figure
210 1), in contrast to the former research [30], involving the pm-rf-APGD-based reaction-
211 discharge system. As shown in Figure 1, the DCF aqueous solution, prepared using either gel
212 or capsule matrix, was delivered to the reaction-discharge system by a Masterflex L/S (Core-
213 Palmer, USA) four-channel peristaltic pump. The flow rate of the DCF-containing solutions

214 was 3.0 mL min⁻¹ or 4.0 mL min⁻¹ for the solutions prepared either using gel or capsules,
215 respectively. The flow rate of the solutions were experimentally chosen in order to ignite
216 stable-in-time FLC-dc-APGD operated in contact with a flowing liquid solution. The FLC-
217 dc-APGD was ignited in the gap between the sharpened tungsten electrode and the flowing
218 liquid cathode, being DCF aqueous solutions based either on gel or capsules formulation.
219 From DC voltage generator (DSC Electronic, DP20H-06PH, Germany), 48 mA discharge
220 current and 1329 V current voltage have been delivered to the system. Connecting electronic
221 hoses either to the tungsten electrode or to the platinum wire attached to the graphite tube
222 provided the electrical contact. Graphite tube (OD = 3.2 mm) was mounted on the quartz
223 capillary (OD = 2.00 mm) through which the proper DCF solutions were delivered to the
224 described system by using a peristaltic pump. After the FLC-dc-APGD treatment, the
225 solutions have been collected into glass vials for further studies.

226
227 **Figure 1.** The FLC-dc-APGD-based reaction-discharge system used for removal of DCF from
228 aqueous solutions prepared either from gel or capsules matrices.

229 **2.3. Assessment of removal efficiency of DCF following FLC-dc-APGD treatment**

230 Aiming to estimate the efficiency of DCF removal following FLC-dc-APGD treatment with
231 the use of HPLC-DAD technique, XR Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) chromatograph with SPD-
232 M20A DAD, SIL-20AC autosampler and LC-20AD pump, was implemented. The
233 temperature of an oven CTO-20AC was set to 27 °C. Gemini-NX (150 x 4.6 mm) column
234 with C18 as stationary phase was utilized for this procedure. The volume of the delivered
235 sample was 25 µL. Gradient elution was applied at the flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹. Ammonium
236 formate at 10 mmol L⁻¹ in addition to 0.1% (m/v) formic acid were used as component A.
237 ACN acted as component B, whose concentration increased during the first 6 mins from 15%
238 to 35%, then remained constant for 2 mins prior to dropping again to 15% during the last 2
239 mins, according to the applied method's gradient. The DCF retention time was 8 mins at 277
240 nm analytical wavelengths. The linearity of response was tested between 0.01 and 200.00 mg
241 L⁻¹ on the analytical standard of DCF. The precision - relative standard deviation (RSD) was
242 lower than 0.9 %, compared to the accuracy enclosing in 95-106%. The limit of
243 quantification (LOQ; the lowest concentration with precision lower than 5%, accuracy
244 between 80-120% and signal to noise 10) was set to 0.01 mg L⁻¹, while the limit of detection
245 (LOD) equalled LOQ/3= 0.003 mg L⁻¹.

246

247 **2.4. Determination of the physicochemical properties of DCF solutions**

248 To assess physicochemical properties of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF solutions in contrast
249 to the corresponding untreated DCF-containing samples, studies involving UV/Vis absorption
250 spectrophotometry, evaluations of Total Organic Carbon (TOC) and Total Nitrogen (TN)
251 contents, in addition to measurements of pH and conductivity have been performed.

252 Regarding UV/Vis measurements, 10-fold diluted untreated and FLC-dc-APGD-
253 treated DCF solutions (100 mg L⁻¹), originating either from gel or capsules matrices, were
254 subjected to analysis using Specord 210 Plus UV/Vis absorption spectrophotometer (Analytik

255 Jena, Germany). The investigated spectral range enclosed in 230-1000 nm with a step of 1
256 nm. The speed of measurements was 10 nm s⁻¹.

257 Moving to TOC analyses, they followed a non-purgeable organic carbon (NPOC)
258 method and were conducted on Analytik Jena Multi N/C 3100 (Germany) equipment. The
259 samples for TOC analyses were prepared as follows: 6.50 mL of the untreated or NTP-treated
260 DCF-containing solutions were acidified with 0.325 mL of 2 mol L⁻¹ HCl. Analogically, the
261 TN analyses have been carried out. The TOC and TN concentrations were presented as
262 means with SD from 2-3 independent measurements.

263 The pH measurements for the untreated and NTP-treated DCF solutions were
264 performed with HI98100 pH-meter (HANNA Instruments Checker Plus, Romania), while the
265 conductivity values of the samples were estimated using the CPC-505 instrument (Elmetron,
266 Poland). In case of pH and conductivity analysis, results were presented as means with SD
267 from 3 independent measurements.

268

269 **2.5. Qualitative and quantitative analyses of RONS produced during FLC-dc-** 270 **APGD operation**

271 Optical emission spectrometry (OES) was implemented for identification of RONS formed in
272 the gaseous atmosphere of FLC-dc-APGD applied for removal of DCF, originating either
273 from gel or capsules matrices. The OES measurements were carried out as follows. The
274 plasma-liquid zone (area between the FLC-dc-APGD discharge and the flowing DCF-
275 containing solution) was collimated on the entrance slit (10 μm) of the Andor Shamrock SR-
276 500i spectrometer (United Kingdom). The emission spectra were recorded within 200-400
277 nm and 400-900 nm spectral ranges using Andor Newton DU-920P-0E CCD camera (United
278 Kingdom) with two holographic gratings 1800 and 1200 lines nm⁻¹, respectively. The CCD
279 camera was operated in full vertical binding (FVB) mode by applying 1 s of integration time.

280 To eliminate second-order radiation, the PG-5 cut-off filter below 400 nm (Zeiss Jena,
281 Germany) was used within the 400-900 nm spectral range. The OES studies were performed
282 for the DCF-containing aqueous solutions prepared basing on gel matrix (50, 100, and 200
283 mg L⁻¹ final concentrations of DCF) or the capsules matrix (25, 50, and 100 mg L⁻¹ final
284 concentrations of DCF) treated with FLC-dc-APGD.

285 Subsequently, in order to reveal the plasma-liquid interactions that led to removal of
286 DCF from the studied solutions, the concentrations of the selected RONS, such as H₂O₂,
287 NO₂⁻, and total ROS were estimated.

288 Firstly, the concentrations of H₂O₂ were determined using a colorimetric assay
289 involving 6.2 mmol L⁻¹ NH₄VO₃ in 5.8 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ [37]. 2.5 mL of the two-times
290 diluted DCF-containing solution was transferred into a glass flask, filled with 2.5 mL of the
291 working mixture with NH₄VO₃, carefully mixed, filled up to the volume of 25 mL with
292 deionized water, mixed, and left at the room temperature for 5 mins. The absorbance values
293 of the resultant orange-coloured solutions comprising peroxovanadium cations (VO₃⁺) were
294 measured at 450 nm using Specord 210 Plus UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena,
295 Germany). The 7-point calibration plot was prepared using a standardized H₂O₂ solution in
296 the concentration ranges of 0-20 mg L⁻¹. The so-estimated H₂O₂ values were presented as
297 means with SD from three independent measurements.

298 Secondly, the concentration of NO₂⁻ ions was estimated using the protocol based on
299 ISO 6635:1984 standard [38]. The calibration curve, which relied on standard sodium nitrite
300 solution and consisted of 6 points within the 0-3.0 mg L⁻¹ range, was plotted. Then, DCF-
301 containing solutions were two-times diluted and 10.0 mL of them were transferred into glass
302 flasks prior to filling with 30 mL of deionized water. Afterwards, 5.0 mL of 0.2% (m/v)
303 sulphanilamide solution and 3.0 mL of 2.25 times diluted 37% HCl were added to the flasks
304 and vigorously mixed. Finally, the 1.0 mL of 0.1% (m/v) N-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine

305 dihydrochloride was added, and the contents was mixed, filled up to the mark of the
306 volumetric flask with deionized water and left for 10 mins at room temperature in the dark.
307 The absorbance values were acquired at 538 nm, using a Specord 210 Plus UV/Vis
308 spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena, Germany). As blank, solution without addition of the
309 nitrite standard was used. The determined concentrations of NO_2^- ions were presented as
310 means with SD from three independent measurements.

311 The amount of total ROS was established by the KI-starch colorimetric method [39].
312 In more detail, the reaction mixture containing 0.3% (m/v) KI and 0.5% (m/v) starch was
313 prepared at 70 °C with support of stirring to get a transparent working solution. After cooling
314 down, 2.9 mL of the so-prepared solution was mixed with 0.1 mL of two times diluted DCF-
315 containing samples, incubated for 1 h at 4 °C prior to conducting measurements at 590 nm
316 with Specord 210 Plus UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena, Germany). As blank, an
317 analogously prepared KI-starch mixture, but without addition of the H_2O_2 standard, was
318 utilized. The nine-point calibration curve from 0 to 30 mg L^{-1} was plotted using a
319 standardized H_2O_2 solution. The concentration of total ROS was depicted as means with SD
320 from three independent measurements.

321

322 **2.6. Ecotoxicity studies on *Lepidium sativum* seeds**

323 To estimate putative environmental impact of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF-containing
324 solutions, prepared either using gel or capsules, in contrast to the corresponding untreated
325 preparations, ecotoxicity studies on *Lepidium sativum* (PL914/32/83/TRZ05) seeds from one
326 batch purchased at a local market were performed. For this purpose, the seeds were sterilized
327 by submerging in 70% ethanol (Avantor Performance Materials, Poland) for 30 s, then
328 washed in sterile deionized water for 1 min, to be finally subjected to 3% H_2O_2 (Avantor
329 Performance Materials, Poland) for 5 mins prior to washing with sterile water 4 times, then

330 seeds were dried with a paper cleaning cloth. Nine of the so-disinfected seeds were placed
331 onto a layer of three sterile qualitative filter paper (ChemLand, Poland) inside a Petri dish and
332 watered using 2.00 mL of either FLC-dc-APGD-treated 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solution (prepared
333 from gel or capsules), the corresponding 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solution non-subjected to NTP
334 treatment, or sterilized deionized water (control). The so-prepared Petri dishes were
335 incubated at 21 °C in dark for 13 days and the watering procedure with DCF-containing
336 solutions was conducted as described above every 3-4 days (watering at days 1st, 3rd, 6th, 9th
337 and 13th). The number of germinated seeds and lengths of *L. sativum* sprouts were measured
338 on the 3rd, 6th, 9th, and 13th day of the experiment, while the weight of the sprouts was
339 assessed on the 13th day. This experiment included 3 biological and 3 technical repetitions,
340 while 9 seeds per Petri dish were considered a single technical replicate. There were therefore
341 5 types of solutions with which the seeds were watered: untreated gel solution of DCF
342 concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹, NTP-treated gel solution of DCF concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹,
343 untreated capsules solution of DCF concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹, NTP-treated capsules
344 solution of DCF concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹ and sterile deionized water as a control, so for
345 each solution 81 seed were included in this analysis. The collected data were presented as
346 means with SD.

347

348 **2.7. Statistical analysis**

349 Comparison of removal efficiencies of different DCF solutions in two matrixes was
350 performed using the one-way ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post
351 hoc test ($p < 0.05$). To compare concentration of DCF between untreated and NTP-treated
352 solutions for particular DCF solutions, Student's t test or Welch's t test was performed ($p <$
353 0.05). For comparison of TOC or TN between untreated and NTP-treated DCF solutions,
354 Welch's t test ($p < 0.05$) was performed. For pH or conductivity comparison between

355 untreated and NTP-treated solutions of different concentrations of DCF Student's t test or
356 Welch's t test ($p < 0.05$) was used. To compare differences of pH decrease between gel and
357 capsules matrix DCF solutions of 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹ during NTP treatment, Student's t test or
358 Welch's t test was performed ($p < 0.05$). In the case of conductivity for this purpose,
359 Student's t test was used ($p < 0.05$). Statistical comparison between the concentrations of
360 certain RONS representatives collected for each concentration of DCF in the same matrix
361 was performed using two-way ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post
362 hoc test (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$). In the case of analysis of
363 number of germinated seeds and lengths of sprouts, Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's multiple
364 comparisons test was used to compare results ($p < 0.05$). For weights results comparison, the
365 one-way ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test was applied
366 ($p < 0.05$).

367

368 **2.8. Cost benefit analysis**

369 To assess the feasibility of the FLC-dc-APGD-based reaction-discharge system for removal
370 of DCF, a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) [40] was conducted with adaptations to the laboratory
371 scale. CBA considers the economic costs associated with the treatment process and the
372 environmental benefits derived from it. The FLC-dc-APGD system was compared to the
373 other DCF removal methods, including other NTP-based approaches, such as pm-rf-APGD
374 [30] and pulsed corona discharge (PCD) [41], as well as photodegradation [42], ozonation
375 [27], and sonolysis [27].

376

377

378

379 **2.8.1. Costs calculations**

380 The cost associated with the treatment of DFC was determined by identifying and quantifying
381 the necessary inputs for its operation, and then incorporating the market value from the
382 appropriate sources. The following categories of costs were considered for all the systems
383 compared in the CBA:

- 384 ● Energy costs (EnC): The systems for treatment of DCF relies on electricity as the
385 source of energy. Hence, the used electricity was calculated and then its market price
386 was used to calculate the costs associated with energy consumption
- 387 ● Equipment costs (EpC): This factor consisted of the initial investment required for
388 setting up the system, including the purchase and installation of all the necessary
389 components of the reaction-discharge system.
- 390 ● Consumables costs (CnC): This value included the costs of all materials or chemicals
391 required for the operation of the reaction-discharge system.
- 392 ● Maintenance costs (MnC): This parameter consisted of expenses incurred in
393 maintaining and repairing the system during operation.

394

395 ***2.8.2. Benefits associated with implementation of technology in the market***

396 Aiming to estimate the benefits of implementation of NTP-based DCF removal systems in
397 the market, the potency of the current approach has been calculated and compared with the
398 other available DCF deactivating devices. The removal efficiency would inevitably dictate
399 the shadow price of DCF [43], a metric representing the negative environmental externalities
400 associated with its presence in aquatic ecosystems [40]. The shadow price, calculated using
401 the distance function methodology, estimates the marginal environmental damage per
402 additional unit of DCF in water. The increased removal efficiency corresponds to a lower
403 shadow price and, consequently, greater environmental benefit derived from implementation
404 of the wastewater treatment. Furthermore, the analysis incorporated other factors affecting

405 the shadow price, such as the simplicity of scalability through the use of a flow-base system.
406 These factors contribute to a comprehensive assessment of the environmental and economic
407 benefits linked with each DCF removal system considered in this analysis.

408

409 **3. Results and Discussion**

410 **3.1. DCF removal efficiency from different aqueous solutions**

411 The NTP-based reaction-discharge system with FLC-dc-APGD was employed for removal of
412 DCF from aqueous solutions, originating from different pharmaceutical matrices, *i.e.* gel or
413 capsules. Concerning gel matrix, 50, 100, and 200 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions have been analysed
414 by HPLC-DAD. Regarding capsules, 25, 50, and 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions have been tested.
415 The average DCF concentration determined in studied solutions along to calculate removal
416 efficiencies are presented in details in Table S1 (Supplementary Information, SI).
417 Considering the removal efficiency of DCF from studied solutions (Figure 2) it can be seen
418 that DCF was removed from the solutions originating from gel matrix more efficiently than
419 these prepared from the capsules matrix. Interestingly, the highest $98.3 \pm 0.05\%$ removal
420 efficiency was determined for gel-based solution containing middle investigated contents of
421 DCF being 100 mg L⁻¹. A different trend was observed for the capsules matrix as the
422 achieved DCF removal efficiency increased together with the raising DCF concentration.
423 While comparing the same DCF concentrations (50 and 100 mg L⁻¹ of DCF), originating
424 either from gel or capsules, it was found that superior removal efficiencies were noted for
425 solutions of pharmaceuticals applied in the gel form rather than capsules. The one-way
426 ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) was
427 performed to compare the removal efficiency of different DCF solutions in two matrixes. It
428 was found that the use of FLC-dc-APGD resulted in a statistically significant more efficient

429 removal of DCF from aqueous solutions of the pharmaceutical preparation in the gel than in
430 capsules for both DCF concentrations of 50 mg L⁻¹ and 100 mg L⁻¹.

431 It is necessary to take into consideration that these preparations differed both in
432 formulation and chemical composition of the matrix. Though, it needs to be stressed that
433 various reaction discharge conditions must have been applied during FLC-dc-APGD
434 treatment of the solutions based on diverse DCF-containing matrices due to issues with NTP
435 ignition. Therefore, the achieved diverse DCF removal rates might be rather associated with
436 variations in the plasma-generating parameters, *i.e.* flow rate of the solution, than the form of
437 pharmaceutical or the excipients included in the studied formulation. However, application of
438 different flow rate of solution was necessary in order to achieve stable-in-time FLC-dc-
439 APGD in contact with proper solutions. Student's t test or Welch's t test ($p < 0.05$) was
440 performed to compare concentration of DCF between untreated and NTP-treated samples for
441 particular DCF solutions. It was found that for all tested DCF concentrations the difference in
442 its concentrations for untreated and NTP-treated solutions is statistically significant.

443

444 **Figure 2.** Removal efficiency [%] of DCF from aqueous solutions, prepared from DCF-containing
445 pharmaceuticals in the form of gel or capsules, which resulted from the applied FLC-dc-APGD

446 treatment. The one-way ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test was
447 performed to compare the removal efficiency of different DCF solutions in two matrixes.

448

449 Chromatograms acquired at 277 nm for 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions, based either on gel
450 or capsules matrices, are shown in Figure 3. In the untreated DCF solutions, the base peak
451 refers to DCF (retention time about 8.0 min) and a minor one occurs. In the FLC-dc-APGD-
452 treated DCF solutions a much lower peak corresponding to DCF was obtained besides several
453 other peaks not previously registered of low intensity. This observation means that there are
454 DCF transformation products in the NTP-treated DCF solutions in addition to probably some
455 dissolved excipients constituting the pharmaceutical matrix. It has to be highlighted that
456 chromatograms displayed in Figure 3 show the separated substances, which have any
457 potential to absorb wavelengths at 287 nm. There are more substances in the solutions with
458 no potential for absorption at the selected wavelengths, for example low mass organics and
459 ions deriving from mineralization.

460

461 **Figure 3.** Chromatograms (extracted for 277 nm) of gel and capsule solutions before and after FLC-
462 dc-APGD treatment (lower part with magnification). The nominal DCF concentration was 100 mg L⁻¹.
463

464

465 **3.2. Changes in the physicochemical properties of DCF after the FLC-dc-APGD** 466 **treatment**

467 The UV/Vis absorption spectrophotometry was used for revealing the changes in the intensity
468 of characteristic bands for DCF in the UV/Vis absorption spectra. Based on the acquired
469 UV/Vis absorption spectra for both matrices used for preparation of DCF solutions (Figure
470 4), a significant decrease in the intensity of the band with maximum absorbance was
471 observed for the treated solutions compared to the untreated ones. Considering the DCF
472 solution prepared using gel and subjected to NTP treatment, the 3 time decreases in
473 absorbance at a wavelength of 276 nm were determined compared to the untreated solution
474 (Figure 4A). Similar findings were estimated for DCF solutions obtained using capsules,
475 however, in this case also the maximum absorbance at a wavelength of 276 nm was noted for
476 the untreated solutions (Figure 4B). Taking into account the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF
477 solution prepared from capsules, a shift in the absorbance maximum towards 373 nm
478 wavelengths was observed (Figure 4B). A putative reason might be an attachment of certain
479 functional groups to the DCF molecule. The change in the color of the solutions from
480 transparent white to yellow as a result of FLC-dc-APGD treatment might suggest that the
481 nitro groups may have been attached to the aromatic ring or rings of the DCF molecule.

482 Having in mind the presented UV/Vis spectra, it was confirmed that better DCF
483 removal was achieved for the solutions prepared from DCF in the form of a gel than in the
484 capsule form. The results from UV/Vis absorption spectrophotometry are in a good
485 agreement with the data collected using HPLC-DAD.

486

487 **Figure 4.** UV/Vis absorption spectra of 10-times diluted DCF solutions prepared either using gel (A)
 488 or capsules (B). The DCF concentration in the studied solutions was 100 mg L⁻¹.

489

490 The TOC and TN analyses were carried out in order to reveal how the FLC-dc-APGD
 491 treatment influenced total organic carbon and nitrogen concentrations in the studied samples
 492 (Figure 5, Table S2 (SI)). For the DCF solutions prepared using a gel matrix, decreases in the
 493 TOC content from 6% for 50 mg L⁻¹ DCF solution to 15% for the 200 mg L⁻¹ DCF were
 494 noted compared to the untreated samples (Figure 5A). Focusing on the capsules matrix, a
 495 different trend was observed. In the case of all the studied solutions, the NTP treatment led to
 496 increases in TOC concentrations from 37% to 49% for 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF, respectively
 497 (Figure 5A). This phenomenon might have been caused by evaporation of solvents during the
 498 applied NTP treatment. Welch's t test was performed to compare TOC between untreated and
 499 NTP-treated samples for solutions with particular DCF concentrations. Based on the research,
 500 it was confirmed that there is statistically significant difference between TOC for untreated and
 501 NTP-treated solutions of DCF concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹ in gel matrix and for all tested
 502 DCF concentration for capsules matrix.

503 Moving to the TN concentration in the FLC-dc-APGD-treated samples prepared from
 504 the gel matrix rises around 124 - 134% for 100 and 200 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions, respectively,
 505 as compared to the untreated ones were remarked (Figure 5B). While the TN concentration in

506 NTP-exposed DCF solutions obtained basing on capsules elevated by approx. 153 - 170 %
 507 for 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF, respectively, as juxtaposed with the untreated samples (Figure
 508 5B). The observed elevation in the TN content for both the investigated types of DCF-
 509 containing solutions could be related to the production of long-lived reactive nitrogen species
 510 (RNS) during NTP operation [30]. Welch's t test was performed to compare TN between
 511 untreated and NTP-treated solutions with particular DCF concentrations. It was confirm that
 512 there is statistically significant difference between TN for untreated and NTP-treated
 513 solutions of each DCF concentration.

514

515 **Figure 5.** TOC concentration (A) determined in the DCF solutions prepared using gel or capsules. TN
 516 contents (B) identified in the DCF solutions prepared using gel or capsules. Means from 2-3 replicates
 517 are depicted for the NTP-exposed (bars with sloping lines) in contrast to the untreated samples (bars

518 in full dark grey color). Welch's t test was performed to compare TOC or TN results between
519 untreated and NTP-treated solutions with particular DCF concentrations (* p < 0.05).

520

521 Considering the pH of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF solutions compared to the
522 untreated ones obtained by gel application, it was found that the used treatment resulted in
523 drop in the pH from 6.68-7.55 to 2.69-3.05 for examined DCF solutions (Figure 6A, Table S3
524 (SI)). Similar observations were found for DCF solutions based on capsules matrix, however,
525 in this case pH decreases from 5.34-5.73 to 2.58-2.75 for investigated DCF solutions (Figure
526 6A). pH comparison between untreated and NTP-treated solutions was performed for
527 different concentrations of DCF using Student's t test or Welch's t test. Using the same tests
528 to compare pH differences between gel and capsules matrix of untreated and NTP-treated
529 DCF solutions, it was found that pH decrease during NTP-treatment is statistically significant
530 higher in case of gel than capsules matrix for both DCF concentrations of 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹.
531 The pH measurements revealed that the FLC-dc-APGD exposure generated highly acidic
532 DCF-containing solutions, in need of neutralization or dilution. The discovered acidification
533 resulting from the NTP-treatment [30, 36] is probably associated with the generated ROS and
534 RNS. For instance, acidic RONS, HNO₃, and HNO₂ could have been produced [30, 36].

535 Passing to examination of the conductivity of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF-
536 containing solutions, the measured values increased after FLC-dc-APGD treatment in all the
537 samples. In more detail, the conductivity rises of approx. 5-12 and 15-32 times, were
538 determined for the DCF solutions prepared from gel and capsules matrices, respectively,
539 compared to the corresponding untreated samples (Figure 6B, Table S4 (SI)). Conductivities
540 of untreated and NTP-treated solutions were compared for different concentrations of DCF
541 using Student's t test or Welch's t test. Furthermore, Student's t test was also used to confirm
542 that conductivity increase during NTP-treatment is statistically significant higher in case of

543 capsules matrix than gel matrix for both DCF concentrations of 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹. We
 544 presume that elevation in the conductivity of the DCF solutions following FLC-dc-APGD
 545 treatment results from the NTP-mediated production of NO₃⁻ and NO₂⁻ ions, as well as
 546 organic acids [30, 36].

547
 548
 549 **Figure 6.** pH (A) and conductivity (B) of the DCF solutions obtained from gel or capsules matrices,
 550 respectively, following FLC-dc-APGD treatment. Means from 3 replicates are depicted for the NTP-
 551 exposed (bars with sloping lines) in contrast to the untreated samples (bars in full dark grey color).
 552 Student's t test or Welch's t test was performed to compare pH or conductivity between untreated and
 553 NTP-treated solutions of different concentrations of DCF (* p < 0.05).
 554

555 **3.3. Qualitative and quantitative analyses of RONS produced during FLC-dc-**
556 **APGD treatment**

557 At the beginning of the studies related to the estimation the role of RONS for DCF removal
558 processes in the studied solutions, the NTP-generated RONS were identified by OES
559 spectrometry. Within the 295-400 nm spectral range (Figure 7A), numerous rotational-
560 vibrational bands of N₂ from the C³Π_u – B³Π_g systems were detected with band heads at
561 296.2 nm (3-1), 297.7 nm (2-0), 315.9 nm (1-0), 337.1 nm (0-0), 353.7 nm (0-1), 357.7 nm
562 (0-1), 371.0 nm (2-4), 375.5 nm (1-3), 380.5 nm (0-2), as well as 389.5 nm (3-6), 394.3 nm
563 (2-5), and 399.8 nm (1-4). The OH radical of A²Σ⁺ - X²Π system was identified with the
564 head at 309.1 nm (0-0) and at 292.9 nm (1-0). In the 400 – 900 nm spectral range (Figure
565 7B), the rotational-vibrational bands of N₂ belonging to C³Π_u – B³Π_g systems with band head
566 at 405.9 nm (0-3) along with N₂⁺ molecules of the B²Σ⁺-X²Σ⁺ system with band heads at
567 420.2 nm (2-3), 427.2 nm (0-1), were identified. Additionally, the ionic oxygen (O II) lines at
568 441.7 nm, 457.6 nm, 465.2 nm, and 470.8 nm and atomic oxygen (O I) lines at 777.2 nm,
569 811.6 nm and 844.7 nm, were noted. Besides, clearly visible atomic lines of hydrogen at
570 486.3 nm (H_β) and 656.4 nm (H_α) were determined. Finally, a strong Na atomic line (Na I)
571 was observed at 589.1 nm. Focusing on the intensities of N₂ and N₂⁺ bands acquired for DCF-
572 containing solutions based on different matrices, the highest intensities were noted for
573 capsules-based preparations (especially for 50 mg L⁻¹ DCF). On the other hand, the most
574 intense OH band head was obtained for the gel matrix (comprising 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF). The
575 intensity of hydrogen lines was significantly elevated for DCF solution based on the gel
576 matrix (200 mg L⁻¹), while the oxygen atomic lines were the strongest for 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF
577 solution, also the gel-deriving formulation. The most intense Na atomic line was obtained for
578 the capsule-based 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solution and its presence may be linked with application
579 of DCF sodium salt exhibiting better solubility. The collected results are in good agreement

580 with our previous work involving the application of the pm-rf-APGD-based reaction-
 581 discharge system for direct degradation of DCF from aqueous solutions, as well as from
 582 synthetic sewage [30]. Accordingly also here, a significant contribution of the $\bullet\text{OH}$, $\bullet\text{H}$, $^1\text{O}_2$,
 583 O_3 , $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ and $\bullet\text{HO}_2$ along with $\bullet\text{N}_2$, $\bullet\text{NO}$, and $\bullet\text{NO}_2$ species, generated during the occurring
 584 plasma-liquid interactions, to degradation of DCF from the solutions based on gel or capsule
 585 matrices, might be suspected.

586 **Figure 7.** Determination of the short lifetime RONS generated between FLC-dc-APGD discharge and
 587 the FLC DCF-containing solutions, based on gel or capsule matrices, recorded in the 200-400 nm (A)
 588 and 400-900 nm (B) spectral ranges by OES.

590 To provide further insight into RONS of longer lifetimes formed during the
591 recombination reactions, colorimetric methods have been used. Considering H₂O₂ in the
592 FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF solutions, the occurrence of these reactive individua is most
593 likely the outcome of recombination of hydroxyl radicals and other highly reactive species
594 that had not been involved in the triggered degradation processes or produced by NTP in high
595 abundance. The defined H₂O₂ contents in the solutions following FLC-dc-APGD exposure,
596 on one hand points to high potency of NTP to generate RONS, while on the other hand
597 suggests the contribution to the reactions of active species of not sufficient oxidative potential
598 to decompose DCF (Figure 8). In general, the determined H₂O₂ concentrations were higher
599 for DCF solutions deriving from gel matrix and increased together with the raising DCF
600 contents (from 4.58±0.35 mg L⁻¹ to 6.88±0.11 mg L⁻¹, Figure 8). Moving to solutions
601 prepared from the capsules matrix, there the H₂O₂ concentration was the highest for 25 mg L⁻¹
602 DCF (4.35±0.15 mg L⁻¹, Figure 8), contrarily to 50 mg L⁻¹ DCF (3.25±0.45 mg L⁻¹, Figure
603 8). In general, no statistical significant difference was observed for H₂O₂ concentration
604 generated in 50 mg L⁻¹ DCF of gel matrix as well as 25 and 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF of capsules
605 matrix. Also no statistical difference can be observed between 100 and 200 mg L⁻¹ DCF of
606 gel matrix. It should be emphasized that the herein-determined H₂O₂ concentrations are rather
607 high, pointing to high incidence of plasma-liquid interactions, presumably owing to the
608 presence of excipients in the investigated pharmaceutical matrices.

609 Passing to the identified NO₂⁻ concentrations, they turned out to be very low, *i.e.* from
610 0.23 ± 0.06 mg L⁻¹ observed for 50 mg L⁻¹ DCF prepared basing on gel matrix to 10.58 ±
611 0.16 mg L⁻¹ noted for 200 mg L⁻¹ DCF also derived from the gel formulation, with the
612 average values not exceeding 1 mg L⁻¹ (Figure 8). A significantly higher NO₂⁻ content in 200
613 mg L⁻¹ DCF prepared from the gel matrix is most likely linked with the highest DCF content,

614 as well as follows a notable boost in the plasma-liquid interactions leading to potent nitrite
615 formation.

616 The oxidative potential of FLC-dc-APGD-treated solutions containing DCF from
617 diverse pharmaceutical sources was studied to unveil i) reactive species that did not
618 participate in the degradation processes and ii) the abundance of recombination reactions of
619 highly reactive RONS of shorter lifetimes, which are not sufficient to participate in
620 degradation process of DCF. Moreover, the defined total ROS concentrations may be
621 connected with the reactions of RONS with two different matrices, leading to generation of
622 secondary species of sufficient oxidative potential to decay DCF. The herein stated total ROS
623 concentration varied from $6.81 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for 100 mg L^{-1} DCF from gel preparation to
624 $10.83 \pm 0.80 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for 100 mg L^{-1} DCF based on the capsules matrix, as can be seen in
625 Figure 8. In terms of the NTP-treated DCF-containing samples prepared from the capsules,
626 the noted total ROS concentrations increased together with the raising DCF concentrations.
627 The opposite situation concerned the gel matrix, as in this case the highest ROS contents
628 were revealed in the solutions of the lowest basal DCF concentrations. The most significant
629 growth in the amount of total ROS, if the separately measured H_2O_2 will be excluded from
630 this consideration, was stated for DCF-containing samples prepared from the capsules matrix.
631 Bearing in mind that in spite of lower basal concentration of DCF, the higher removal
632 efficiencies were observed for solutions based on the capsules-type medication, the defined
633 elevation in the total ROS contents seems correlated with the decay-associated data. The
634 presence of excipients in the capsule matrix most likely scavenged the activity of short
635 lifetime ROS, as well as promoted their recombination, which found reflection in the stated
636 total ROS concentration. Particularly interesting results involved 100 mg L^{-1} DCF solutions
637 in the gel matrix, in which the total ROS concentration resulted mostly from the determined
638 H_2O_2 concentration ($6.81 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $6.53 \pm 0.15 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, respectively). As also the

639 highest removal efficiency was observed for this sample, the established greatest contribution
640 of H₂O₂ to the total ROS population seems well correlated with the hypothesis on the
641 recombination processes of ROS that do not participate in the DCF degradation process.
642 Referring to the herein identified RONS concentrations in the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF
643 solutions, they are in line with our former studies on DCF removal, in which pm-rf-APGD
644 was applied as the NTP source. In the latter studies, the determined H₂O₂ concentrations did
645 not exceed 6.0 mg L⁻¹ [30]. On the other hand, the total ROS contents was 2-times higher
646 [30] than described in the current work. Summing up, most likely the abundant presence of
647 ROS in the FLC-dc-APGD-treated DCF-containing samples resulted from the dominating
648 involvement of highly reactive species of short lifetimes such as •H, •OH, •O₂⁻, and •HO₂.
649 Post their generation, short-lived RONS recombined to RONS representatives of longer
650 lifetimes such as H₂O₂, •CO⁻, NO₂⁻, NO₃⁻, among others.

651 **Figure 8.** Quantitative analyses of long lifetime RONS, produced during FLC-dc-APGD operation, in
 652 the DCF-containing aqueous solutions from either gel or capsules matrices. The two-way ANOVA
 653 analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test (pairwise comparison presented as
 654 compact letter display for $p < 0.05$) was performed to compare the concentration of NO_2^- ; H_2O_2 , and
 655 total ROS in DCF containing solutions with different contribution in two matrixes.
 656

657
 658 **3.4. Ecotoxicity studies of the NTP-treated in contrast to the untreated DCF-**
 659 **containing solutions**

660 In the process of purifying aqueous solutions from organic substances of detrimental
 661 environmental effects, such as pharmaceuticals, it is necessary to provide an insight into the
 662 toxicity of the solutions exposed to the NTP action [44].

663 Having this in mind, we examined putative ecotoxicity of FLC-dc-APGD-treated
664 solutions in contrast to the corresponding untreated 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions (prepared
665 either from gel or capsules matrices) and sterile H₂O, by evaluation of the early growth of the
666 accordingly watered *L. sativum*. In this regard, number of germinated seed and the lengths of
667 the *L. sativum* sprouts at the consecutive 3rd, 6th, 9th and 13th days of the experiment, and the
668 final weight after 13 days were determined.

669 Average numbers of germinated seeds watered using untreated DCF gel solution,
670 NTP-treated DCF gel solution, untreated DCF capsules solution, NTP-treated DCF capsules
671 solution and sterile deionized water, after 3 days from the start of experiment were as
672 follows: 9±1, 9±1, 9±1, 9±1, 9±1, and for 13 days after start of experiment 9±1, 9±1, 9±1,
673 9±1, 9±0, respectively (Figure 9A, Table S5 (SI)). Average number of germinated seeds
674 watered with all tested solutions at each day was compare using Kruskal-Wallis test with
675 Dunn's multiple comparisons test, which showed that there is no significant difference
676 between them. Thus, watering the seeds with NTP-treated DCF solutions did not affect the
677 number of germinated seeds of *L. sativum*.

678 The measured average length of *L. sativum* sprouts with SD, watered using untreated
679 DCF gel solution, NTP-treated DCF gel solution, untreated DCF capsules solution, NTP-
680 treated DCF capsules solution, or sterile deionized water, were as follows: 2.6±1.0; 2.9±0.3,
681 3.0±0.4; 3.0±0.6 and 3.0±0.9 cm (after 3 days of experiment start) and increased up to
682 4.5±0.8; 4.9±0.5; 4.8±0.6; 4.6±0.7, and 5.3±0.8 cm (after 13 days of experiment start),
683 respectively (Figure 9B, Table S6 (SI)). An average length of sprouts, which were watered
684 with described above solutions, was compare using Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's multiple
685 comparisons test. This test proved, that for each day there is no significant difference between
686 its lengths. Therefore, there is no impact of watering the seeds with NTP-treated DCF
687 solutions on length of *L. sativum* sprouts.

688 Considering the average weight of *L. sativum* sprouts, determined after 13 days after
689 start of the experiment, the results collected for untreated DCF gel solution, NTP-treated
690 DCF gel solution, untreated DCF capsules solution, NTP-treated DCF capsules solution, and
691 sterile deionized water, were as follows: 0.3530 ± 0.0860 ; 0.3998 ± 0.0667 ; 0.3166 ± 0.0576 ;
692 0.4064 ± 0.0646 , and 0.3441 ± 0.0678 (Table S7, SI). For weights of sprouts comparison, the
693 one-way ANOVA analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test was used. It
694 was confirm that there is no significant difference between weights of sprouts, which were
695 watered using untreated DCF gel solution, NTP-treated DCF gel solution and sterile
696 deionized water. Therefore, there is no negative impact of plasma treatment of solutions used
697 for watering on weights of sprouts. Moreover, it has been proven that in case of DCF
698 capsules solutions, for sprouts that were watered with NTP-treated solutions, there is
699 significant greater weight, than in case of untreated one. Consequently, it can be concluded
700 that NTP-treatment of DCF capsules solutions for watering *L. sativum* sprouts cause increase
701 in the weight of sprouts.

702

703 **Figure 9.** The average number of germinated seeds (A), length (B) and weight (C) of *L. sativum*
 704 sprouts, watered using NTP-treated 100 mg L⁻¹ DCF solutions (prepared either from gel or capsules
 705 matrices), the corresponding untreated DCF solutions and sterile distilled water as a control. The
 706 sprouts lengths were measured on the 3rd, 6th, 9th, and 13th day from the start of the experiment. The
 707 weight of the plants was determined on 13th day from the start of the study. To compare results of
 708 number of germinated seeds and lengths of sprouts, Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's multiple

709 comparisons test was performed. For comparison of weights of sprouts, the one-way ANOVA
710 analysis with the Tukey's multiple comparisons post hoc test was used.

711

712 **3.5. Results of the cost-benefit analysis**

713 In this section, we present the CBA of the treatment with FLC-dc-APGD-based reaction-
714 discharge system for removal of DCF, compare it with the other existing DCF deactivation
715 methods, namely pm-rf-APGD [30], photodegradation [42], ozonation [27], and sonolysis
716 [27]. The costs were calculated in Euros, after converting the Polish National Zloty (PLN) to
717 Euro using the exchange rate of National Bank of Poland: 1 Euro = 4.259 PLN, 2024-07-11
718 [45]. The observations regarding the FLC-dc-APGD reaction-discharge system were recorded
719 during this study, while the data for the rest of the analysed treatments originated from the
720 literature including the previous works of the authors.

721 **3.5.1. Costs associated with the DCF treatment**

722 To calculate the costs associated with each treatment process, the energy, equipment,
723 consumables, and maintenance cost were estimated for a lab level setup. A summary of the
724 costs for various systems has been presented in the Table 1. Energy costs were calculated
725 based on the electricity consumption per L of the treated solution and assumed electricity
726 price of 0.176 Euro/kWh. Equipment costs considered the initial investment for each system,
727 while maintenance costs accounted for periodic component replacements, such as weekly
728 exchanges of the pin-type tungsten electrodes and silicone hoses in the first two NTP
729 systems, substitution of the tungsten wire in the PCD system, and consideration of warranty
730 periods for the UV lamp in the photodegradation system, the ozone supply system in the
731 ozonation system, and the ultrasonic liquid processor in the sonolysis system. No additional
732 consumables were identified for the plasma-based systems and sonolysis, except for the

733 energy costs considered. Only in the photodegradation system, one Petri dish (0.128
 734 Euro/dish) per L of pollutant-containing solution is to be accounted for as a consumable.
 735 Considering the flow rate of the solution as 3.5 mL per min, overall 8322 hrs of operation per
 736 year, 5% maintenance and downtime, it is estimated that a total volume of 1747.62 litres
 737 ($8322 \text{ hrs} \times 60 \text{ mins} \times 3.5 \text{ mL min}^{-1} \div 1000$) of liquids would be treated annually.

738 **Table 1** Comparison of costs for various methods of DCF removal.

Treatment	EnC	EpC	MnC	Total annual cost (TNC) calculation	TNC in
Method	(Euro/L)	(Euro)	(Euro/year)	(Euro/year)	Euro/year
FLC-dc-APGD	0.062	7520.545	2197.699	$9718.244 + (0.2658 \times 1747.62)$	9827.311
pm-rf-APGD	0.047	7520.545	2197.699	$9718.244 + (0.1994 \times 1747.62)$	9800.065
PCD	0.005	5524.771	610.472	$6135.243 + (0.02025 \times 1747.62)$	6143.552
Photodegradation	0.029	1898.446	221.581*	$2120.027 + (0.124999 \times 1747.62)$	2171.319
Ozonation	0.042	340.456	(included in	$340.456 + (0.18 \times 1747.62)$	414.316
Sonolysis	0.132	5977.225	EpC)	$5977.225 + (0.5625 \times 1747.62)$	6208.039

739 * *Consumable*

740 3.5.2. Benefits associated with the DCF treatment

741 Two key factors were assessed for each system: the removal efficiency of DCF and the flow-
 742 through configuration. The flow system, in particular, offers advantages for large-scale
 743 applications, as it supports continuous operation, which is essential for scalable and industrial
 744 uses. Table 2 presents the summary of findings for the benefits associated with the DCF
 745 treatment methods. The findings for FLC-dc-APGD system were the results by the authors

746 during this study, whereas the findings for the rest of the systems were drawn for comparing
 747 purposes from the literature.

748

749 **Table 2.** Comparison of benefits for various methods of DCF treatment.

Treatment	DCF Removal	Flow	Source
Method	Efficiency [%]	configuration	
FLC-dc-APGD	98.3	Yes	Authors' findings
pm-rf-APGD	74.8	Yes	[30]
PCD	>95	Yes	[41]
Photodegradation	98	No	[42]
Ozonation	Almost complete	No	[27]
Sonolysis	55	No	[27]

751

752 3.5.3. Summary of the CBA analysis

753 The CBA analysis revealed that the FLC-dc-APGD system, while initially more expensive
 754 due to the required investment in specialized equipment, presents a superior option in the
 755 long run for *e.g.* in the implementation of this technology to the market. This assumption
 756 relies on a combination of factors that outweigh the higher upfront cost. Firstly, the FLC-dc-
 757 APGD system demonstrates high efficiency in DCF removal, reaching 98.3%, which is
 758 crucial for potently addressing decontamination of wastewaters from pollution of
 759 pharmaceutical origin. The above-presented decomposition rate translates to releasing a
 760 lower amount of active DCF into the environment, thereby reducing putative ecological

761 damage and limits the associated costs. Secondly, comparing FLC-dc-APGD system with
762 photodegradation, ozonation and sonolysis, only the first one is a flow-based system. The
763 flow-based system is particularly advantageous for large-scale operations, as it enables
764 continuous processing, which is crucial for scalability and industrial applications. In the case
765 of the remaining systems, *i.e.*, pm-rf-APGD and PCD, they are also flow-based, however
766 with their use, a lower removal efficiency of DCF was achieved. Hence, the superior
767 efficiency of FLC-dc-APGD, justify its higher initial cost by providing substantial long-term
768 economic benefits. Additionally, the fact that this is a flow system increases the potential for
769 real-world application by enabling the scaling up of DCF removal for continuous processes.

770

771 **4. Conclusions**

772 Here, the FLC-dc-APGD reaction-discharge system was applied for removal of DCF from
773 aqueous solutions, prepared either using gel or capsules matrices, with efficacy ranging from
774 89.6 to 98.3%. Following NTP-treatment, the TOC and TN contents increased in terms of the
775 DCF solutions based on the capsules matrix, while regarding the gel-based DCF solutions,
776 the provided exposure to FLC-dc-APGD resulted in elevations of TN solely, contrarily to the
777 TOC. Passing to physicochemical analyses, notable drops in the pH in addition to significant
778 increases in the conductivity of the NTP-treated solutions, with little dependence on the basal
779 source of DCF, were observed. The noted decay of DCF resulted most probably from the
780 identified RONS. Ecotoxicity assays of the so-obtained effluents towards *L. sativum* seeds
781 did not reveal negative effects on the early plant growth. The CBA showed that the FLC-dc-
782 APGD system, while initially more expensive in contrast to the other investigated systems
783 due to the required investment in a specialized equipment, presents a superior option in the
784 long run due to a combination of factors that outweigh the higher upfront cost. It is
785 recommended that the regulatory bodies should advocate for policies that provide financial

786 incentives or subsidies for adopting advanced non-thermal plasma technologies like FLC-dc-
787 APGD. Also, further research should be conducted to optimize the FLC-dc-APGD system,
788 potentially reducing its initial and operational costs, and scaling up for treatment of the
789 municipal water supply. Additionally, increasing public awareness about the environmental
790 impacts of pharmaceutical pollutants and the benefits of advanced removal systems, like
791 FLC-dc-APGD, is crucial.

792

793 **Supplementary Information**

794 This article contains Supplementary Information

795

796 **Declaration of competing interests**

797 Authors declare no competing interests

798

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812

813 **Author contributions**

814 A.D. was responsible for conceptualization of the presented study. K.L. supervised by A.D.
815 used cold atmospheric pressure plasma-based technology for removal of diclofenac from
816 aqueous solution prepared from different pharmaceutical matrices. A.D. and P.J. adjusted the
817 plasma-based reaction-discharge system. K.L. determined physicochemical properties of the
818 plasma-treated in contrast to non-treated diclofenac solutions. M.C. conducted HPLC-DAD
819 studies, analysed, and described the obtained results. K.L. supervised by A.D. performed
820 ecotoxicity studies. K.L. analyzed and visualized the collected data. D.T. was involved in
821 determination of the concentrations of RONS in the studied solutions, analysed and described
822 the results. Y.C. carried out cost benefit analysis. P.J., P.C, and A.M.P. corrected the
823 manuscript. P.P. took part in the discussion. P.C. was responsible for open-science-policy and
824 data storage. K.L., Y.C., M.C, D.T., and A.D. prepared the first draft of this article. A.D. and
825 Y.C. got funding for this research and were responsible for administration of the projects. All
826 Authors agreed to the final version of this manuscript.

827

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